

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Informal Settlement and Teenage Prostitution in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria

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GSC Advanced Research and Reviews, 2021, 06(03), 011–018

Publication history: Received on 23 January 2021; revised on 26 February 2021; accepted on 01 March 2021

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/gscarr.2021.6.3.0033>

Abstract

Informal settlement which sometimes used as synonym of slum, has over the years led to various social problems such as prostitution and many others. Base on this, the paper examined informal settlement and teenage prostitution in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State. Two objectives were raised as guide to the study. The study area is Yenagoa which is the capital city of Bayelsa State. The study used the survey design, and also adopted primary and secondary sources. 150 respondents constituted the population size and purposive sampling technique was also adopted. Mean and standard deviation and t-test constitutes the method for data analysis. The findings revealed that urban slum settlement and poor family background are responsible for teenage prostitution in Yenagoa. The study concludes and recommends for urban renewal programme for the slum dwellers as well as government and other institution even individuals to embark on economic empowerment programmes for slum dwellers.

Keywords: Bayelsa; Deviant acts; Informal settlements; Prostitution; Slums; Vulnerable children

1. Introduction

Informal settlement, over the years has remained a permanent feature of most cities. This is irrespective of whether the city is in third world or developed country. It is essentially a product of or a pointer to the existence of inequality. This phenomenon is more prevalence in third world nations. United Nations (2003) Habitat report reveal that about 33% of urban population in developing countries live in sum and that the highest percentage of this (approximately 62%) live in slum area. This report equally report that the total number of urban slum dwellers will increase to about two billion if no meaningful or joint efforts are made to address the phenomenon. Its emergence in most cities in the world, especially in Africa according to Livinus, Tamunomiete and Yiinu (2009) signify that slums constitute crucial dements in contemporary urbanization issues.

As observed by McManu (2020) informal settlements are slums and that over the years, its spread have grown. Using Port Harcourt as its study, the study claimed that its providence is due to migration of people to the city for the purpose of working for job opportunities. Slums are phenomenal and it constitutes a product of failed planning policies and lack of political will to improve conditions of slum dwellers. Given this overview, slum area is mainly peopled by low income earners. Such land lack security of tenure; access to improved water, poor sanitation and are exposed to multiple health and security problems. It is this general drive for meaningful economic life that informs the emergence of slum. As predominantly poor residential area, Childslumz-school (2019) described children who reside in this area as vulnerable children. On this basis, slums areas breed criminality and harbor delinquent offenders (Omole and Owoeye, 2011). That is, slums are breeding ground for majority of social problems in the cities. Omole and Owoeye (2011) claimed that an

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informal settlement provides hideout for criminal gangsters. It is on this basis that most urban renewal programmes are predicated on. In support of this, Njoku and Okoro (2014) argue that high criminal rate inform the use of alcoholism, psychological issues making suicide common in urban slum. This relationship therefore makes this work imperative.

2. The problem

Generally, informal settlement, also called slum or unplanned settlement is not limited to developing countries. It is a reaction of people towards not just unavailability of housing, but affordability of existing houses. It is a function of rapid urban growth. This phenomenon, according to United Nations Habitat Development Context and Millennium Agenda (2002), about 2 billion people will be living in such informal settlement by 2030 if major changes are not made in urban management policies. Critical in slum prevalence in urban environment is that slums especially in Nigeria are attributed to rural – urban migration for job opportunities (Ebakpa and Brisiba, 2019). According to these scholars, slum or informal settlement play crucial role in the urban scenery and have the potential of housing the poor due to its affordability and availability.

In the context of unplanned settlement's attributes, very low income people live there. This over time has become the basis why Nubi (2015), Ekpenyong, Nyenge and Mathias (2019) claimed that slum communities are veritable breeding grounds for criminality. Ekpenyong and Mathias (2019) study of urban slums and youth criminality in Bayelsa State Nigeria: A study of selected slum settlements in Yenagoa metropolis confirms that there is high incidence of youth criminality in Yenagoa slums. Among the deviant acts observed are prostitution, steeling and robbery. These scholars also established that residence dire poor economic condition coupled with moral breakdown and the lack of visible law is critical elements in the existence of the observed delinquent acts.

Similar studies by Bodo (2019) confirm that prostitution constitutes one of the vices in typical Nigeria city and that it is caused by massive rural –urban migration. Reaffirming these scholars work, Azibasuan (2019) in a related study established that Yenegoa, just like any other Nigeria cities have slums: Obele, Gwegwe, hospital junction, Tombia and that many more are still springing up. The scholar observed that in these **slums brother**, beer parlors, restaurants and guest houses within the slum attract quite a number of teenagers and adolescents who usually hang around the premises in an attempt to find clients as a means of raising quick money to meet up with the day to day social realities of life.

2.1. Objectives of the Study

- To establish if the existence of slum provide a natural cover for teenagers' involvement in prostitution.
- To establish if teenagers' involvement in prostitution, is related to their poor family background.

2.2. Area of the Study

Yenagoa is the capital of Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The primary economic activity of the residence is fishing and business. The city becomes administrative capital of Bayelsa in 1996 on the creation of the state by General Sanni Abacha. The city is bounded by Mbiama communities of Rivers State in the North and East by Kolokoma/Opokuma Local Government on the West (Idoko, 2016). As a local government, it comprises of twenty one communities. Its population size, according to 2010 National population commission report is about 352, 285. Yenegoa has an equatorial type of climate. The monthly temperature is 25°C to 31°C (Idoko, Ndiweri, Ogali, and Ikegbulan, 2016).

3. Methodology

This work is a survey research. Data were collected through questionnaire and secondary sources. The population of the study is 150 respondents. These are mainly teenage prostitutes. The study made use of purposive sampling technique. The collected data were analyzed through mean and standard deviation.

3.1. Literature Review

Generally informal settlement and prostitution have had plethora definitions. In some instances, informal settlement for example is substituted with slum, marginal land or unplanned settlement. As for slum, some scholars see it loosely as a crowded, dilapidated area lacking basic social amenities. Drawing from this informal settlement has been conceived as an area heavily inhabited by the poor; such area is noted for poor sanitation, wretched living conditions. It is simply a degraded area with heavy population and this population is predominantly poor. Conceptualizing this, UN-Habitat (2007) described informal settlement as slum. Such settlement, according to UN-Habitat (2007) is characterized by

substandard housing and squalor. Of great interest in all these, is that slum is not a planned environment and it is a neglected settlement often found in urban area. It is also a pointer to the existence of inequality in housing.

Prostitution unlike slum suffer similar definition problem. Feminist abolitionists whose interest is to end prostitution agree that prostitution is not just a profession, but the oldest profession in the world. This group however disagree that it is a job like any other job. Using the cases in New Zealand, Germany Denmark, Netherland and Australia where prostitution is considered as job, the body disagree that prostitution is not skill as conceived by these. That if prostitution is “sex work”, then rapists is theft. The inside of a woman’s body should not be seen as a workplace. What is clear is that the liberalist sees prostitution as a work and legal while feminist abolitionist see it as illegal. That is, engaging in sexual activity in exchange for payment is bad. Generally, the act involves indiscriminant sexual relationship for exchange for money.

Given the link between the two concepts, Ekpenyong and Mathias (2019) in their separate studies have established close link between slum area and deviant activities. Nubi (2015) called slum a “breeding ground of crime as stagnant water is to mosquitoes. Ekpenyong and Mathias (2019) among the deviant acts identified in their study of the relationship between slum and youth criminality is the prevalence of prostitution. Walim, Garba and Shimfe (2019) also established a strong link between living in slum and anti-social behavior. Azibasuum (2019) in a similar study established a link between social vice like teenage prostitution, drug and smulggling. Several studies on deviant behavior over the years have established a strong link between poverty, housing pattern or environment generally as a stimulant to deviant act. Informal settlements according to Meth (2017) in a study of informal housing, gender crime and violence: The role of design in urban South Africa concludes that informal settlements are criminalized by space and their residence often criminalized by association. It is on this basis that Rivers State Government over the years destroyed slums in Port Harcourt, Nigeria in its urban renewal programme.

4. Analysis and Presentation of Data

In order to give a directional empirical touch to this study two groups of respondents were considered, classified as groups I and ii. Group 1 constituted 150 inhabitants of slums and group ii consisted of 50 teenage prostitutes, in Yenegoa in BayelsaState.

4.1. Administration and retrieval of research instrument

Table 1 Administration and retrieval of research instrument

Group	Constitution of group	Number of copies administration	Number retrieved	Percentage returned (%)
I	Inhabitants of slums	150	150	100
Ii	Teenage prostitutes	50	50	100

The concept of drop-and-pick was adopted in the administration and retrieval of the copies of the research instrument. The responses of the respondents were used to answer the research questions and analyze the stated hypotheses for this study.

5. Research question one

Standard reference mean of the five (5) point Likert rating scale is 3.00. Table 2 depicts that the mean ratings of the items measured are each greater than the standard reference mean of 3.00 therefore are all deployed in the analysis of hypothesis one. It further reveals that the associated standard deviations are small which indicates homogeneity of the responses of the respondents.

Table 2 Relationship between slum existence and teenage prostitution in Yenegoa, Bayelsa, State.

Questionnaire Items	Level of Acquiescence					Total #	Mean (x)	Std der
	SA	A	N	D	SD			
Increase in urban slum Promotes Teenage prostitution	62	45	3	25	15	150	3.76	1.39
	27	13	1	6	3	50	4.10	1.25
The sale/taking of alcoholicdrinks in slum areas enhance promiscuity of the girl child	75	55	5	9	6	150	4.23	1.04
	20	14	2	10	4	50	3.72	1.37
Teenagers move from rural to urbanSlums for prostitution	70	50	7	13	10	150	4.05	1.21
	23	17	4	5	1	50	4.12	1.05

Source: Survey Data, 2021

Key: Strongly agree (SD) =5, Agree (A) = 4, Neutral (N) = 3, Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1

6. Hypothesis One

6.1. Ho₁

There is no significant relationship between slum existence and teenage prostitution in Yenegoa, Bayelsa State. i.e; Ho₁: rho (e) = 0

Ha₁: There is significant relationship between slum growth and teenage prostitution in Yenegoa, Bayelsa State. i.e; Ha₁: e ≠ 0 (i.e., a two-tailed test)

Computation of coefficient of correlation

Table 3 Computation of coefficient of correlation, rho (e):

S/N	Group 1	Group ii	R ₁	R ₂	D = R ₁ - R ₂	D ²
1	62	27	3	1	2	4
2.	45	13	6	6	0	0
3.	3	1	15	14.5	0.5	0.25
4.	25	6	7	8	-1	1
5.	15	3	8	12	-4	16
6.	75	20	1	3	-2	4
7.	55	14	4	5	-1	1
8.	5	2	14	13	1	1
9.	9	10	11	7	4	16
10.	6	4	13	10.5	2.5	6.25
11.	70	23	2	2	0	0
12.	50	17	5	4	1	1
13.	7	4	12	10.5	1.5	2.25
14.	13	5	9	9	0	0
15.	10	1	10	14.5	-4.5	20.25
						<u>73.00</u>

6.2. Coefficient formula

$$\text{Rho}(e) = 1 - \frac{6\sum D^2}{n(n^2-1)}$$

We have

$$E = 1 - \frac{6 \times 73}{15(15^2-1)} = 0.8696$$

Therefore, $e \times \sqrt{\frac{n-2}{1-e^2}}$

We have; $t_{cal} = 0.8696 \times \sqrt{\frac{15-2}{1-0.8696^2}}$

Therefore, $t_{cal} = 6.350$

Means and standard deviations of the sets of data;

Table 4 Computation of means and standard deviations of the sets of generated data.

X ₁	X ₂	x ₁ ²	x ₂ ²
3.76	4.10	14.1376	16.8100
4.23	3.72	17.8929	13.8384
4.05	4.12	16.4025	16.9744
12.04	11.94	48.4330	47.6228

$\bar{x}_1 = 4.01, N_1=150, S_1^2 = 0.3164, S_1 = 0.563$

$\bar{x}_2 = 3.98, N_2 =50, S_2^2 = 0.8954, S_2 = 0.946$

At a level of significance of 5% and number of degrees of freedom of 13, the critical value of t, for a two-tailed test, is 2.160

Decision: $t_{cal} > t_{critical}$, fail to accept Ho₁

Results are presented in a tabular form as depicted below

Table 5 The t test of relationships between Slum Growth and Teenage Prostitution in Yenegoa.

Group	Mean (x̄)	Std Dev	N	Df	t _{cal}	t _{critical}	Decision
I	4.01	0.563	15	1.3	6.350	2.160	Reject Ho ₁

6.3. Research Question Two

Table 6 Showing a relationship between prostitutes poor family background and their engagement in prostitution in Yenegoa.

Questionnaire Items	Level of Acquiescence					Total #	Mean (x)	Std. Dev.
	SA	A	N	D	SD			
Poor family background is the main course of teenage prostitution	65	50	5	20	10	150	3.93	1.26
	24	16	2	5	3	50	4.06	1.21
Teenage prostitutes are the main source of economic sustenance of their parents and family members.	78	52	3	7	10	150	4.21	1.13
	23	15	1	9	2	50	3.96	1.25

Source: Survey Data, 2021

Table 6 shows that the main reason why most teenagers engage on prostitution is because of their parents' poor economic statuses. It is not just a means for these teenage prostitutes to meet their own needs but that of their parents and other family dependents.

6.4. Hypothesis Two

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between teenage prostitutes' poor family background and their involvement in prostitution in Yenegoa, Bayelsa State.

i.e; Ho₂: e = 0

Ha₂:There is significant relationship between teenage prostitutes' poor family background and their involvement prostitution in Yenegoa, Bayelsa State.

i.e;e≠0 (i.e., 2 tailed test)

Coefficient of correlation, rho(e) of the sets of data

Table 7 Computation of rho (e):

S/N	Group 1	Group ii	R ₁	R ₂	D = R ₁ - R ₂	D ²
1	65	24	2	1	1	1
2.	50	16	4	3	1	1
3.	5	2	9	7.5	1.5	2.25
4.	20	5	5	6	-1	1
5.	10	3	6.5	9	-2.5	6.25
6.	78	23	1	2	-1	1
7.	52	15	3	4	-1	1
8.	3	1	10	10	0	0
9.	7	9	8	5	3	9
10.	10	2	6.5	7.5	-1	$\frac{1}{23.50}$

Applying spearman rank correlation coefficient formula:

$$\text{Rho (e)} = 1 - \frac{6\sum D^2}{n(n^2-1)}$$

We have:

$$e = 1 - \frac{6 \times 23.50}{10(10^2-1)} = 0.8576$$

Therefore, e =0.8576 or 85.76%

Test of hypothesis two:

Test statistic: n=10; t-test is appropriate

Number of degrees of freedom(df) is 8.

Applying the t-test formula:

$$T = e \times \sqrt{\frac{n-2}{1-e^2}}$$

We have:

$$T = 0.8576 \times \sqrt{\frac{10-2}{1-0.8576^2}}$$

Therefore, $t_{cal} = 4.716$

Means and standard deviations of the sets of data:

Table 8 Computation of means and standard deviations of the sets of data:

X ₁	X ₂	x ₁ ²	x ₂ ²
3.93	4.06	15.4449	16.4836
4.21	3.96	17.7241	15.6816
8.14	8.02	33.1690	32.1652

$$\bar{x}_1 = 4.07, N_1=150, S_1^2 = 0.2182, S_1 = 0.467$$

$$\bar{x}_2 = 4.01, N_2 =50, S_2^2 = 0.6176, S_2 = 0.786$$

At a level of significance of 0.05 and number of degrees of freedom of 8, the critical value of t, for a 2-tailed test, is 2.228

Decision: $t_{cal} > t_{critical}$, reject Ho₂

The results are presented in a tabular form as depicted below:

Table 9 T test of the relationship between teenage prostitutes poor family background involvement in prostitution in Yenegoa

proGroup	Mean (\bar{x})	Std Dev	N	Df	t _{cal}	t _{critical}	Decision
I	4.07	0.467	10	8	4.716	2.228	Reject Ho ₂
II	4.01	0.786					

7. Conclusion

Drawing from the above, it is glaring that slums exist in the Yenegoa just like any other city in the world. The presence of this provided the needed impetus for other vices including teenage prostitution. Of great concern in the existence of teenage prostitution is that slum environment is a marginal environment, as such the cost of housing is easily affordable by the low income group. Secondly, as a marginal land, the layout of the area makes it attractive or convenient for other deviant stimulants like drugs to exist.

Based on these, it is expedient for government and other institution even individuals to embark on economic empowerment programmes for slum dwellers. Such programme should include compulsory primary and secondary education for those who are interested in schooling. Skill acquisition programmes like hair dressing and barbing saloon is important here. If possible such people after training programme should be established with start-up capital. In this, it is necessary for government to monitor the progress of the business. Other businesses training like bead and hat making, catering services, computer operation and sewing are essential here.

Equally important is that there should be urban renewal programme for the slum dwellers. In this case, affordable houses with layouts should be built for slum dwellers. The need to address migration and unemployment problem is

urgent here. To do this, it is necessary for government evenly distribute social infrastructure between rural area and urban area. This is important because it is the current urban bias development style that is the pull factor for excessive rural urban migration; a phenomenon that is the root cause of informal urban settlement development.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

We are indebted to Chinago Alexander for his encouragement, support and time to see that this work is published and on time.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

There is no conflict. This work is original work by us.

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